

Building D1 at Magdala Revisited in the Light of Public Fountain Architecture in the Late-Hellenistic East*

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ABSTRACT: The small columnar Building D1 discovered at Magdala in the early 1970s was first identified by the excavators as a mini-synagogue. Although Ehud Netzer has convincingly opposed this view, arguing that the building functioned as a fountain house, some scholars challenge Netzer's identification, most notably on the basis of a doubtful comparison with a supposedly canonic type of Roman nymphaeum. Consequently, alternative interpretations for the function of this building, such as a synagogue or a latrine, continue to appear in the literature. This paper argues that the building has not been compared to the right category of public fountains. Indeed, Magdala's Building D1 presents strong similarities with contemporary examples of late-Hellenistic fountain architecture in Asia Minor and fits perfectly within the context of the long-term evolution of the so-called *stoa*-shaped fountain houses. The function of Building D1 as a fountain house, as argued by Netzer, seems very likely, particularly on the basis of comparative data from the city of Sagalassos (south-west Turkey).

INTRODUCTION

In the early 1970s, a small columnar building was discovered during excavation of the Roman settlement of Magdala, a site situated beneath the remains of the Arab village of el-Mejdel at the north-western shore of the Sea of Galilee. The excavators identified this structure as a 'mini-synagogue' during its initial phase of construction, before its supposed transformation into a water reservoir at a later date (Corbo 1974: 19–32; 1976: 365–371). Ehud Netzer, however, has opposed this view and argued that the building, which is better known as 'Building D1', was intended as a fountain house from the outset and never as a synagogue (Netzer 1987). Though the latter proposal has gained some support among scholars (Levine 1996: 428, n. 5; 2000: 72; Aviam 1997; Binder 1999: 193–196;

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Runesson 2001: 175, n. 18; Leibner 2009: 215), others have challenged it on the grounds that it does not fit within Magdala's supposed Jewish cultural profile according to literary sources and that its type is not comparable with that of Roman nymphaea (e.g., Corbo 1976: 370–371; Ruf 1995: 83; Zangenberg 2001: 24–29). Consequently, according to some scholars, the excavators' identification of the building as a synagogue remains valid (Strange 1992; Richardson 1996: 104, n. 6; de Boer 1997: 22; Dunn 2004: 303, n. 220; Kaswalder 2009: 271), whereas others have opted for alternative interpretations, such as a bathhouse (Meyers and Kraabel 1986: 179), a fishpond (Strange 1992), or a latrine (Zangenberg 2001; 2003: 96; 2010: 476).¹

Both arguments to reject Netzer's identification of Building D1 as a fountain house were first raised by the excavators themselves (Corbo 1976: 370–371). The first argument — that the building does not fit within the cultural profile of Magdala in that period — is largely based on literary sources depicting a town with a predominantly Jewish population. As Zangenberg (2001: 20–21), however, has convincingly demonstrated, using this argument to discard the interpretation as a fountain house seems ill-founded. Rejecting the existence of a 'Roman-style' fountain house as not fitting a literary-based 'Jewish' cultural profile is flawed, belittles archaeology's independence as a historical discipline and seems to be a circular argument. The existence at Magdala of Hellenistic or Roman elements, such as a fountain house in this case, bears no relationship with any cultural profile for that settlement. The meaning of such elements is elastic and not static, and depends upon the context in which those elements are perceived and how they are used (see, e.g., Woolf 1998; Stewart 2008).

The second argument for rejecting Netzer's claim seems more firmly rooted in the scholarly literature. The excavators' assertion (Corbo 1976: 370–371) that Building D1 does not conform in size or shape to the typical picture of nymphaea in the Roman world is still considered valid by several scholars. Through a misreading of Netzer's identification of Building D1, scholars have consequently referred to it as a 'nicht völlig befriedigend' and 'ein ungewöhnliches Exemplar eines Nymphäums' (Ruf 1995: 83; Zangenberg 2001: 29). Indeed, when one compares Building D1 at Magdala with the second-century CE Roman nymphaea found in such cities as Gadara, Bosra, Scythopolis, Gerasa and Olympia, it is clear that this analogy does not hold (see Zangenberg 2001: 24–28). Nor does a comparison with a late-Republican private nymphaeum in Italy seem convincing (Ruf 1995: 78–79). Netzer, however, never actually referred to Building D1 as a nymphaeum in his article — except when mentioning the excavators' alternative

1 The fact that the original ground plan (Corbo 1974: fig. 8; 1976: fig. 1) showed no drawing basin may have strengthened the hypothesis that the building was a synagogue.

proposal — but interpreted it instead as בית המעיין ('fountain house'; cf. Netzer 1987: 166).²

It will be argued here that the claim for rejecting the identification of Building D1 as a fountain house seems flawed. Simply stated, the building has not been compared to the right category of public fountains. Hence, statements such as 'Bedauerlicherweise mangelt es Netzers Argumentation an typologischen Beispielen von vergleichbaren Nymphäen' seem irrelevant (Ruf 1995: 83; Zangenberg 2001: 24). Indeed, the monument presents stronger similarities with contemporary examples of late-Hellenistic fountain houses in Asia Minor, and fits perfectly within the long-term evolution of the so-called *stoa*-shaped fountain houses also known as 'Brunnenhäusern in Hallenform' in German. On the basis of comparative data from the Roman city of Sagalassos (south-west Turkey) in particular, Building D1's function as a fountain house seems very likely.

Before placing Building D1 within the context of fountain architecture in the Graeco-Roman East, a general description of the structure is presented and its context in the Roman settlement of Magdala is given.

BUILDING D1 AT MAGDALA

The Roman settlement of Magdala has long been identified, on the basis of literary accounts, as the birthplace of Mary Magdalene (e.g., Manns 1976; Kaswaller 2002: 162).³ For this and other reasons (Corbo 1974), this settlement has been the focus of various archaeological investigations since the early 1970s. These investigations have revealed a large settlement founded during the second century BCE on an area extending over c. 9–10 hectares, from the Sea of Galilee in the east to the foot of Mt. Arbel in the west. The large-scale excavations conducted by the Franciscans — now termed the SBF-Magdala Project — have been confined to the south-east zone of this ancient settlement. Though its centre should be sought some 100 metres to the north-west of the excavated area, the architecture and artefacts retrieved here suggest that Magdala was a prosperous urban settlement, especially during the first century BCE and first century CE. The regularly planned street grid, the existence of a well-planned water distribution system, and the presence of an urban villa, public buildings and leisure facilities, such as a

2 It remains possible that although he did not refer to it explicitly, Netzer may have had a nymphaeum in mind. It is striking that many scholars — both those who concurred with him and those who rejected his proposal — adopted this term to refer to Building D1 (see, in addition to the already cited sources, Levine 1996: 428, n. 5; 2000: 72; Leibner 2009: 215).

3 Magdala has also been associated with the location of Tarichaea (Albright 1921–22: 29–46), but this identification has recently been questioned by Kokkinos (2010), who locates Tarichaea — following Pliny the Elder (*Natural History* 5.71) — to the south of Tiberias.

bathhouse, a fountain, a harbour, a *quadriporticus* and a recently-discovered first-century synagogue, all seem to support this view (for an extensive overview of the city's history in light of the most recent archaeological findings, see De Luca 2009).

Building D1, discovered in the early 1970s (Corbo 1974: 19–32; 1976: 365–371) and recently reinvestigated (De Luca 2009: 376–378), is situated to the south-east of a crossroads between streets V2 and V3, oriented north-south and east-west respectively, in the vicinity of a water spring (fig. 1). The building was surrounded by an extensive network of water channels and installations. To the east of the building a stepped water basin (D3) can be found, connected to another building (D2) with a yet unknown water-related function. North of these two structures, another yet unidentified water-related structure (D7), possibly a latrine, was built from re-used materials (De Luca 2009: 376). North of D7 and south of street V3, a water channel (D8), connected to Building D1, ran in a west–east orientation. In the late fourth century CE, the terminal installations of a new aqueduct, occupying part of the space of the earlier street V2, were installed to the west of Building D1. In addition to the aqueduct bridge, running in a south–north direction, an earlier tower and a series of large water basins (A1–A8) were identified. A section of these installations (A8) was partially laid over the

Fig. 1. Building D1 of Magdala and environs: ground plan (©SBF-Magdala Project)

collapsed west wall of Building D1, indicating that the waterworks must have functioned once the former was already out of use.

The external dimensions of Building D1 (figs. 1–2) were 8.16×7.25 m. Its walls were made out of basalt ashlar masonry (north-east wall: 0.73 m. thick; west wall: 0.76 m. thick; south wall: 0.78 m. thick). The masonry consisted of 0.35–0.37 m. thick courses made of two rows of ashlar, with mortar and stone chips filling the interstices. The building’s interior (5.87×6.57 m.) was characterised by a continuous U-shaped draw basin with its three arms along the west, south and east walls, surrounding a quadrangular courtyard. The draw basin was

Fig. 2. Building D1 of Magdala: ground plan and section (©SBF-Magdala Project)

limited at the front by a colonnade consisting of seven columns. All were of a sober Doric style and were situated *c.* 1 m. from the exterior walls. The two northernmost columns were placed *c.* 2.2 m. from the northern wall of the building. Five of the columns were rounded (0.33 m. in diameter), while the two in the south-east and south-west corners were heart-shaped. Forming a continuous border behind these columns stood a set of vertical parapet plates (0.71–0.76 m. high; 0.30 m. thick basalt slabs), whose upper inner side was rounded, most probably to facilitate the vertical pouring of drawing vessels (fig. 3).

Limiting the central space to the north, across the entire width, a staircase of five steps (0.19–0.25 m. high) has been found, four of which are still *in situ*. In accordance with the former interpretations of the building as a synagogue, these steps were long thought to be benches. However, even though the entrance of the building has not been revealed in the excavations (Corbo 1976; De Luca 2009), the location of Building D1 with respect to street V3 suggests that its entrance must have been here on the north side (fig. 1). Therefore, these steps should be interpreted as a staircase, not as benches (see also Netzer 1987: 165; Zangenberg 2001: 23).

The quadrangular courtyard in the centre of the building presented two distinct phases, with two floor levels made of basalt slabs uncovered one above the other (fig. 2). The original floor has been dated to the late first century BCE, on the basis of pottery sherds found below the foundation level of the northern staircase

Fig. 3. Building D1 of Magdala: view from the south-east (©SBF-Magdala Project)

(Loffreda 1976: 339). Sometime during the first century CE, another floor was laid 0.35 m. above the original (Corbo 1974: 26; 1976: 370; De Luca 2009: 377). This renovation of the building probably became necessary because the lowest floor had become flooded at some point by the surrounding springs (Netzer 1987: 170). During the second construction phase, the building underwent other renovations as well. For instance, two parapet slabs limiting the southern arm of the U-shaped draw basin were placed between the columns, thus enlarging the capacity of the draw basin (fig. 3). In addition, in the south-east of the building a second, smaller, entrance was constructed, providing access to the building from street V4 via a bridge made of three slabs laid longitudinally over the water collector.⁴ On the basis of ceramic and numismatic evidence found on the floor level, it could be concluded that the building, as well as the adjacent structures to its east (D2, D3, D7), were probably abandoned around the fourth century CE (Corbo 1976: 370; De Luca 2009: 377).

The recent excavations by the SBF-Magdala Project have confirmed that Building D1 served a water-related function from the outset (De Luca 2009: 376–377). Several hydraulic features involved in the supply and drainage of water were documented. The building was originally situated 1 m. below the level of adjoining streets V2 and V3. Water originating from active springs in the immediate surroundings entered Building D1 through various openings from the north and south-west sides. A channel coming from Building C3, which received the water directly from the water spring to its north, ran underneath street V3 and the staircase of Building D1 to feed the draw basin from the north (Corbo 1976: 366). Three flat rectangular inlets, two in the south and one in the west wall, also guaranteed the flow of clean water (De Luca 2009: 377). The most recent excavation has shown that the eastern arm of the U-shaped draw basin tilted several degrees to the south, the southern arm of the basin tilted slightly to the east, and the eastern arm tilted *c.* 3 cm. to the north (De Luca: personal communication).⁵ All this ensured that the water could flow out of the building through a tailpipe in the north-east of the building towards water channel D8. Before the later raising of the floor, a closed gate system allowed adjusting the level and flow of water from the tailpipe to D8. After renovation, however, the system was rendered useless. In the second phase, a pipe in the south-east corner of Building D1 released the collected water into Building D2 and eventually into water basin D3 (figs. 1–2) (De Luca 2009: 377).

4 Although four slabs are visible in the original plan (Corbo 1974: fig. 9), recent excavations have demonstrated that there were only three (De Luca 2009: tav. 14, 15, fig. 56; see also Corbo 1974: fig. 16).

5 In the recent excavation report (De Luca 2009: 376–377), the description of the water system is not sufficiently detailed.

STOA-SHAPED FOUNTAIN HOUSES IN THE GRAECO-ROMAN EAST

In antiquity, water had to be drawn from a natural source and brought to where it was to be used or consumed (Tölle-Kastenbein 1990: 130; Crouch 1993: 19–31, 283–285). Rudimentary installations built at springs were the first manifestation of this basic necessity of human communities. Depending on the local geology, springs were tapped either below ground level or at the front of a cliff. From late-Minoan times onwards (Glaser 1983: 105–106; 2000: 416–417), the easiest way to collect water was to build a sunken basin accessible via steps, ensuring convenient access to the water table regardless of its natural fluctuations. When water had to be tapped at the front of a cliff, a collection pipe or gallery bringing water to a basin was preferred (Dunkley 1935–36: 142–144).

The exposure of water to sunlight and dust quickly triggered the practice of sheltering the installation under a roof, becoming *de facto* the first expression of public fountain architecture. Sources on the earliest columnar fountain houses remain scanty. Terracotta models from Lemnos (Dunkley 1935–36: 149–151), dated to the ninth–seventh centuries BCE, evidence the early existence of small constructions with columnar displays. From the sixth century BCE onwards, numerous depictions on painted vases illustrate, with a certain degree of visual inaccuracy, the typology of contemporary fountain houses (Hülse 1919: 73–80; Dunkley 1935–36: 152–171; Glaser 1983: 107–108; 2000: 414–416; Tölle-Kastenbein 1990: 131–138). Sheltered under a pitched or gabled roof, these generally large, isolated buildings were fronted by a columnar display in the Doric order (fig. 4). Archaeologically attested from the second half of the sixth century BCE, the earliest columnar fountain houses were likely the work of tyrants in their benevolent willingness to improve sanitation and wellness (Glaser 1983: 107–108; 2000: 419–422; Tölle-Kastenbein 1994). Until the middle of the fourth century BCE, the typology of these columnar public fountains could vary significantly, depending on the local topography and the built environment (Dorl-Klingenschmid 2001: 30–31). Elongated, squarish, *pi*- or L-shaped ground plans could invariably be chosen. Variations in length, elevation, amount and type of supports or roof types were also frequent.

In late-Classical times, columnar fountain houses continued to be built, but of smaller proportions compared to their Archaic predecessors. In the middle of the fourth century BCE, the formal experimentation characterising the earlier examples was followed by the fixation of a canonic type in Attica and its broader surroundings (Dunkley 1935–36: 183–187; Dorl-Klingenschmid 2001: 31). These late-Classical/early-Hellenistic fountain houses were divided into two longitudinal naves with the water basin occupying the interior one. The front nave, accessible via a columnar display, formed a sheltered vestibule. The length of the building and the configuration of the façade could vary according to the size of the aqueduct and the available space. In Asia Minor and its environs, two

Fig. 4. Depiction of an Archaic fountain house (after Tölle-Kastenbein 1990: fig. 83)

variants of this canonic type became popular from late-Classical times onwards (Dunkley 1935–36: 187–188; Dorl-Klingenschmid 2001: 31–33). The first variant is the small, squarish *in antis* fountain in the Doric style (Glaser 1983: 110–112; 2000: 424–429). This trend also appeared in continental Greece, evident, for example, in the third- or second-century BCE fountain houses in the gymnasium of Sicyon (fig. 5) (Glaser 1983; Agusta-Boularot 2001: 217–218). A second variant of fountains reached impressive lengths, such as the second-century BCE *Stadtbrunnen* in Pergamon and its 21 m. long Doric portico. The well-preserved fountain of Ialysos (Rhodes), dated to the fourth (Glaser 1983: 48–49; Agusta-Boularot 2001: 216–217) or the third century BCE (Glaser 2000: 425), is a good representative of this second type: the hexastyle Doric fountain, covered with a pitched roof, was divided into two naves of equal depth. The basin, occupying the interior nave, was limited at the front by a high parapet inserted between pillars and provided with spouts in the shape of lions' heads (fig. 6).

Later in Hellenistic times, fountain houses could be reduced to a single wide nave, whereby the draw basin filled the totality of the inner space and was lined by a parapet inserted between the supports composing the façade (Dorl-Klingenschmid 2001: 33–34). In some cases, the inner space was still divided into two naves, yet both were occupied by the basin. This structural modification is

Fig. 5. Elevation of Fountain A in Gymnasium of Sicyon (after Glaser 1983: fig. 95)

Fig. 6. Elevation of the mid-fourth-century BCE fountain house of Ialysos (after Glaser 1983: fig. 90)

crucial for the long-term evolution of fountain architecture: the greater exposure of water, now brought at the level of the façade without any intermediary vestibule, opens the way to Roman nymphaea. From late-Classical/early-Hellenistic times, greater liberty was also taken in the choice and arrangement of the columnar orders. Fountain houses of the two canonic types were built in the Ionic or

Corinthian orders, such as the Laodikè Fountain at Miletos (Dorl-Klingenschmid 2001: 214–215; Tuttahs 2001: 35–43), built between 259 and 253 BCE.

From the middle-Hellenistic period onwards, the distance taken with the traditional orders found a parallel in ground plans. To the almost perfect visual uniformity characterising endless colonnades succeeded a marked central axis. The mid-second-century BCE fountain house of Tenos (Glaser 1983: 87–89; Augusta-Boulatot 2001: 219–220) consisted of two lateral wings in the Doric order, each sheltering a basin occupying the whole interior. In the middle, a central exedra equipped with benches interrupted the rhythm of the façade.

The same logic underscores another type of ground plan popular in the late-Hellenistic/early-Imperial period: the U-shaped Doric colonnaded fountain house. So far, two examples of that type are known from Sagalassos and Pisidian Antioch, both in south-west Turkey. The fountain house of Pisidian Antioch was later turned into a nymphaeum and its early phases could not be documented accurately (Owens 2008). The Doric Fountain of Sagalassos (figs. 7–8), described in greater detail below, was built in the late first century BCE. It is the fountain showing the greatest similarities with Building D1 from Magdala in terms of ground plan, elevation, size and hydraulic apparatus. Just before the advent of fully open-air fountains in early Augustan times, the U-shaped fountain house was the product of a long evolution combining influences from every period: a colonnade in the Doric order sheltering the water basin, the reduction to one nave

Fig. 7. Front view of the Doric Fountain of Sagalassos after completion of the excavations (©Sagalassos Archaeological Research Project)

Fig. 8. Front view of the Doric Fountain of Sagalassos after anastylosis (©Sagalassos Archaeological Research Project)

with a basin filling the whole interior space and, finally, the visual centralisation of the façade. A comparison between the Doric Fountain of Sagalassos and Building D1 at Magdala demonstrates that the latter not only presented all the characteristics of a U-shaped fountain house, but also fits perfectly within the long-term evolution of these installations.

THE DORIC FOUNTAIN OF SAGALASSOS: THE MISSING PARALLEL FOR BUILDING D1 AT MAGDALA?

The Doric fountain house of Sagalassos was found in an excellent state of preservation. Excavated between 1990 and 1992, it was the object of a full anastylosis programme which also included the complete refurbishment of the original hydraulic apparatus (figs. 7–8). Dated by means of stratigraphic deposits to the late first century BCE, the fountain underwent more or less important alterations in the late Antonine period and in late antiquity (Waelkens 1993; Waelkens *et al.* 1995; Waelkens 1997; 2000; 2002: 317–318). The Doric Fountain was originally erected in the context of the planned expansion of a domestic area towards the east, at some distance from the monumental centre. The fountain was partially built into the slope of the terrain, a fact that probably explains its unusual plan designed to retain the earth of the hill. Like in Magdala, this lower level compared

to the surroundings may also have facilitated the tapping of aquifers. This was the principle applied in the earliest stepped fountains mentioned above.

Like Building D1 at Magdala, the Doric Fountain consisted of three Doric porticoes in a U-shaped arrangement framing a quadrangular courtyard (fig. 9). The colonnade sheltered a continuous, U-shaped draw basin. The dimensions of the two buildings were almost identical on the outside; the fountain measured 10.90×7.33 m., whereas the inner surface of the courtyard was 6.68 m. long and 5.08 m. wide. The width of the draw basin varied, from 1.12 to 1.22 m. to the north, to 1.26 m. in the eastern portico and 1.14 m. to the west. The basin was limited at the front by a continuous parapet set on top of a single step. It consisted of thick limestone slabs (0.73–0.79 m. high; 0.34–0.42 m. thick) with a moulded

Fig. 9. Ground plan of the Doric Fountain at Sagalassos (©Sagalassos Archaeological Research Project)

profile at the base and at the top. Unlike in Building D1, where the parapet slabs formed a continuous border behind the columns (in the original building phase at least, see above), the parapet of the Doric Fountain supported the columns composing the porticoes. Below each of these supports, it assumed the shape of slightly projecting half-pedestals, 0.42–0.44 m. wide. The elevation consisted of 2.47 m. high half-Doric columns set against quadrangular pillars. The inner corners of the courtyard were heart-shaped, consisting of pillars with half-columns on the two adjoining sides. Architrave-frieze blocks decorated with olive wreaths on some of the metopes were crowned with a cornice displaying lion-headed false waterspouts.

During the first building phase, the water basin was fed through a single, flat and rectangular waterspout inserted into the back wall of the north portico. Just above, a Doric window, originally closed with a wooden shutter, gave access to a service room located behind the façade. The Doric Fountain was fed from a local aquifer. The drainage was ensured via a terracotta pipe inserted at the south-west edge of the water basin, which evacuated water into a system consisting of several settling basins. This indicates that the drained water was probably recycled to feed other hydraulic structures in the city. In the early sixth century CE, the Doric Fountain went out of use. The hydraulic apparatus was totally refurbished and the fountain turned into a genuine *castellum divisorium*. The entire interior of the building was filled with debris as high as the top of the basins' parapets. Three terracotta conduits were then laid over the debris. Running over the courtyard and along the north and west arms of the water basin, these pipelines supplied hydraulic structures in the city.

In sum, it seems clear that Building D1 at Magdala presents too many similarities with the Doric Fountain of Sagalassos to continue rejecting its identification as a fountain house. Despite their geographic remoteness, the two contemporary buildings share the same architectural configuration, almost identical dimensions and roughly comparable hydro-technical features. Nevertheless, establishing links between two architecturally comparable buildings found in different regions remains dangerous. Typology should stay at the level of comparison and should not be exploited to presuppose historical links that were absent in this case. Even in the best documented cases, the various reasons underlying the diffusion of architectural motifs and formulae remain hard to delineate.

DISCUSSION

In the past, the small columnar Building D1 at Magdala has been repeatedly reinterpreted differently, creating a confusing picture with regard to its exact function. Though Netzer's identification as a fountain house has been acknowledged by several scholars, many sceptics remain.

Zangenberg, for instance, recently rejected Netzer's claim on the basis of a

lack of close parallels (Zangenberg 2001: 24–29), although — as he himself is aware (Zangenberg 2001: 32) — his own interpretation of the building as a latrine lacks such parallels too. Indeed, a detailed examination of some technical features of Building D1 casts some doubt on this hypothesis. First, the continuous groove necessary to anchor latrine seats in the back wall is not present. Second, the upper profile of the parapet slabs, rounded towards the inside, would be highly impractical for fixing the front part of the seats (see also Zangenberg 2001: 40–41). Finally and most important, recent excavations have demonstrated that at least in its second building phase, the water drained out of Building D1 would run into structures D2 and D3 (see above). The obvious recycling of water into these two structures identified as draw basins makes the interpretation as a latrine highly unlikely.

The reluctance to interpret Building D1 as a fountain house is predominantly based on an analogy with a supposed canonic type of Roman nymphaeum found in the Levant. However, as we have made clear, it was not Ehud Netzer but the excavator Virgilio Corbo who made, and subsequently rejected, this possible analogy. Thus, as we have demonstrated, a rejection of Netzer's claim on the basis of this analogy is flawed. Simply stated, the building has not been compared to the right category of public fountains.

We have shown that Building D1 fits perfectly within the late evolution of the so-called *stoa*-shaped fountain houses. Based on a late-Hellenistic parallel from Sagalassos in south-west Turkey, we have argued that the tapping of local springs, the U-shaped draw basin and its profiled parapets, the sober Doric porticoes sheltering the installations and the general spatial organisation of the building all plead, without any doubt, for an identification of Building D1 as a public fountain house.

The existence of a public fountain house at Magdala fits perfectly in the picture of its 'urban' and 'Mediterranean' cultural profile that is emerging in recent scholarship (see Aviam 1997: 399; De Luca 2009: 442–445; Leibner 2009: 221–227; Zangenberg 2010: 475–478). The archaeological excavations have demonstrated that Josephus' identification of this settlement as 'polis' or 'town' (*Bellum Judaicum*, 2.252) seems justified. In the past, scholars dismissed this term as not in keeping with Magdala's size and character (Goodman 1983: 27; Safrai 1994: 36). Note, however, that Pausanias (10.4.1) did not reject the definition of the Greek settlement of Panopeos as a 'polis' on the grounds of its small size, but basically because of its lack of an 'urban' appearance. Indeed, in contrast to its earlier Classical and Hellenistic definition, there seems to have been an emphasis in Roman times on the physical attributes and urban amenities of a town (e.g., Lomas 1997: 23). One such urban amenity strengthening Josephus' identification of Magdala as a 'polis' would be a public fountain house such as Building D1.

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